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LAWS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES OF TEENAGE ATHLETES

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Abstract. *In this article, in the previous volleyball game, attacking shots were performed mainly by vertical jumps, but in recent years, the implementation of these skills from the defensive zone has become increasingly stronger, and the ability to jump in the diagonal (height to length) direction has also been consistently formed. it is highlighted that it is necessary.*

Keywords: *volleyball players, physical qualities, exercises, teenage athletes, speed, loading.*

INTRODUCTION

In the process of training young volleyball players, especially at the initial training stage, it is one of the most urgent issues of volleyball practice, proving the effectiveness of using traditional and non-traditional exercises that develop agility.

Many specialists have conducted scientific research on the issues of movement functions, age-specific characteristics and development of physical qualities of teenage athletes. According to them, childhood is an important stage for long-term physical development and a favorable period for starting sports training. The main tasks in the training of young athletes are strengthening the health of children and comprehensive physical development, making a gradual transition to the chosen sport in a goal-oriented manner, increasing the level of physical fitness based on learning the techniques of the chosen sport. , is the selection of promising young athletes for further training in the chosen sport.

R.D. Khalmukhamedov and others in the methodical instructions for conducting training sessions for the program intended for young athletes are the basis for mastering boxing techniques and tactics of regular general and special physical training. emphasized that. At the same time, for the comprehensive development of strength, quickness, coordination and endurance, exercises performed in gymnastic shells: climbing a rope and a stick, walking on a stilt, exercises on a horizontal bar, parallel bars, hoops, jumping with support; athletics exercises (running high jumps, throws and throws, cross-country

running, short-distance running) were recommended as effective means. development has age characteristics, namely:

- the development of various physical qualities occurs heterochronously;
- the magnitudes of annual growth are not the same at different age periods and differ in their relative magnitudes when growth is compared;
- in most children of primary and secondary school age, the indicators of physical qualities are different according to their level (for example, the level of strength, static endurance, as a rule, does not correspond to the level of dynamic endurance);
- a special exercise conducted with one method during physical loads of the same size and intensity allows to compare the data of children of different ages, genders and physically developed, different pedagogical effects are achieved;
- during the period of natural growth of the level of development of physical qualities in teenage athletes (sensitive periods) is much higher than the average level of development of the same qualities in children and adolescents who do not play sports;
- at each age, the level of development of physical qualities differs in representatives of various types of sports. It is accepted to say that physical qualities are separate aspects of human movement capabilities.

The structural foundations of the development of physical qualities are related to the progressive morphological and biochemical changes in the musculoskeletal system, central and peripheral nervous system, and internal organs. Based on this, the level of development of physical qualities directly depends on the compatibility of somatic and vegetative functions.

Active and sports games are very important for effective training of quickness of movements. It is known that during long-term uniform muscle activity and when one or other difficulties arise, protective inhibition associated with the feeling of fatigue develops earlier in children and adolescents than in adults. On the development of speed quality

I.V. Lyakh developed the following methodological rules for performing exercises:

- exercise in technique should not be complicated;
- the exercises should be well mastered by the participants;
- the duration of the exercises should be such that it does not decrease due to rapid exhaustion at the end of its performance;
- the duration of quick exercises should not exceed 16-17 seconds in children and teenagers;
- the next exercises are performed in the recovery phase;
- active rest should be used before repeating quick exercises, which can last 1-2 minutes;
- quick exercises are performed among the first in training.

The training program for 12-13-year-old schoolchildren includes sports games, relay races, movement games, strength and flexibility exercises, various jumps, gymnastics and acrobatic exercises, low and high start runs. , it is desirable to include long jumps.

In the process of training speed, it is necessary to strive to maximize the speed of movements that do not require great muscle tension, to ensure the optimal amplitude of movements as much as possible, and to maximally relax the muscle groups that are not involved in the performance of work.

According to the sources, high-speed gymnastic exercises, short-distance running, and basketball game provide a good opportunity to comprehensively train movement speed and agility in wrestling.

Therefore, as mentioned above, children and adolescents can better withstand short-term loads of various sizes. Due to this, while training with them, it is necessary to train agility and other physical qualities by using various means of training (including movement and sports games) and methods, while teaching sports techniques. should be worked on.

Age-specific norms of physical activity for boys are as follows: for the spine - from 45 to 60 repetitions, for the hip joint - from 30 to 35 repetitions on each leg , for the joints of the shoulder girdle - from 25 to 35 repetitions in each hand. Exercises are repeated in a series - 3-5 rhythmic repetitions are performed with a gradual increase in amplitude.

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